

length/greatest width = 1.4.

5 males: length = 1,150-1,248 µm, stylet = 16.5 µm, length/greatest width = 150-175, spicule = 11.5 µm.

20 second-stage juveniles: length = 42040 µm, length/greatest width =

25-27, length/esophagus length = 3.44.0, length/tail length = 6.0-6.5, stylet = 11.5-12 µm.

Measurements and the perineal pattern of females indicated the species is *Meloidogyne graminicola* Golden and

Birchfield. The nematode is found in Orissa, Assam, and Tripura States of India; Bangladesh; Thailand; and Louisiana, United States. This is the first record of the nematode in West Bengal. □

Control of rice root nematode

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Rice root nematode *Hirschmaniella oryzae* is an important rice pest in India and other countries. Nematode populations are high in flooded, heavy alluvial soils.

Nursery and root-soak pesticide appli-

cations were tested for nematode control on IR20 at two locations in Tamil Nadu in 1980-81 (see table). Treatments were replicated thrice in 4-m² nursery beds and 2 × 1 m plots at 20 × 15 cm spacing.

Root samples were collected at monthly intervals until harvest by randomly uprooting one plant from each plot. Nematodes separated from the roots by the Baermann pan technique were counted.

Grain yield, plant height, root length, and root weight were recorded.

Nematode populations ranged from 18 to 270 per 5 g of root examined from different treatments (see table).

Application of carbofuran 3% G at 1 kg ai/ha in the nursery at sowing, followed by phenamiphos or carbosulfone 0.2% root soak, significantly reduced nematode populations and increased grain yield. □

Effect of pesticides on rice root nematode at 2 locations, Tamil Nadu, India.^a

Nematicide		Aduthurai					Sirugamani				
Seedbed	Seedling root soak	Popu- lation (TV)	Plant ht (cm)	Roots		Grain yield (kg/2 m ²)	Popu- lation (crv)	Plant ht (cm)	Roots		Grain yield ² (kg/2 m ²)
				Length (cm)	Weight (g)				Length (cm)	Weight (g)	
Carbofuran 3% G 1 kg ai/ha	Carbosulfone 24 EC at 0.2% concn	6.35	94.0	30.0	27.3	0.67	7.57	77.7	32.3	28.0	0.75
Carbofuran 3% G 1 kg ai/ha	Phenamiphos 40 EC at 0.2% concn	7.17	94.3	30.3	19.0	0.71	5.70	82.3	36.7	30.0	0.78
Metham sodium 77.5 kg ai/ha	Dimethoate 30 EC at 0.2%	9.90	84.0	23.7	17.0	0.42	8.10	79.3	33.0	23.3	0.45
Metham sodium 77.5 kg ai/ha	-	10.20	89.7	27.7	25.3	0.41	9.87	78.3	32.0	21.7	0.47
Untreated check C. D.		11.63	81.7	31.3	20.0	0.41	13.20	70.7	28.7	22.0	0.39
		1.33	N.S.	4.0	3.7	0.061	1.33	6.0	4.57	N.S.	0.06

^aMeans for 3 replications. ^bTV = transformed values of $\sqrt{x+0.5}$ where 'x' stands for the nematode population.

Pest management and control WEEDS

Effect of planting density and submergence level on weed density in rice fields

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Effect of planting density and submergence level on weed density was recorded at 70 sites in Nadia District, West Bengal, during the 1981 wet season. Sites were planted with medium-duration improved rice varieties.

1. Relationship between planting density and weed density.

Planting density and submergence level were significantly but negatively correlated with and substantially affected weed density. Weed density decreased from 84 to 10 weeds/m² when planting density was increased from 15 to 42 hills/m² (Fig. 1). Increasing submergence level from 0.0 to 6.5 cm reduced weed density from 94 to 20 weeds/m² (Fig. 2). □

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2. Relationship between submergence and weed density.

Soil and crop management

Influence of seed rate and timing of fertilizer application on wet seeded rice yield

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Transplanted rice area in the central plain of Thailand is diminishing and wet seeded rice area is increasing, especially in irrigated systems. An experiment to determine optimum seed rate and timing of fertilizer application for wet seeded rice was

Effect of seed rate and time of fertilizer application on grain yield of RD7 rice (av of 4 replications). Suphan Buri Rice Experiment Station, 1981 dry season.

Time of fertilizer application ^a	Grain yield (t/ha) at seed rate of			Mean yield ^b (t/ha)
	62 kg/ha	94 kg/ha	125 kg/ha	
Incorporated BS	5.5	4.9	5.2	5.2a
10 DS	5.5	5.1	4.9	5.2a
20 DS	5.5	4.8	5.2	5.2a
30 DS	5.5	5.1	4.9	5.2a
40 DS	5.1	4.6	4.8	4.8 b
Mean	5.4	4.9	5.0	
				F value ^c
Seed rate (R)				8.30*
CV (a)	8.7%			
Time of fertilizer application (T)				4.02**
R × T				< 1 ^{ns}
CV (b)	5.5%			

^aBS = before sowing, DS = days after sowing. ^bMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different among themselves. ^c*Significant at 5% level; **significant at 1% level. ns = non-significant. LSD 0.05 for 2 seed rate means = 0.1 t/ha.

conducted at SBRES during the 1981 dry season.

Soil at the experimental site was Nakhon Pathom clay, with pH 5.1, 2.97% organic matter, and cation exchange capacity 22 meq/100 g soil. Pregerminated seeds were sown at 62, 94, and 125 kg/ha. Ammonium phosphate (16-20-0) at 219 kg/ha was applied at different times after sowing and 200 kg ammonium sulfate (21% N)/ha was applied at panicle initiation.

Results showed that 62 kg seed/ha was optimum and suggested that chemical fertilizer can be applied up to 30 days after sowing (see table). □

Effect on ratoon rice of cutting height and time of nitrogen application on the main crop

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Ratoon rice may increase production where limited rainfall and soil moisture reduce cropping intensity. We studied the effect of main-crop management practices on the performance of ratoon rice at the IRRI farm July 1980 to January 1981.

Nitrogen was applied on breeding line IR9784-2-3-2 as described in Table 1. The main crop was harvested by cutting 5 cm and 15 cm above soil surface and by ani-ani (a method where only the panicles are cut). Plants were cut to 15 cm 7 days after the ani-ani harvest. Two days after harvest 40 kg N/ha was applied to all plots. To encourage tiller growth, fields were flooded with 2-3 cm water 2-3 days after harvest. Water depth was gradually increased to 5-7 cm and maintained at that level until grain ripened.

Nitrogen application at different main-crop plant growth stages did not affect grain yield or other plant characters of the main crop (Table 1). Yield was not influenced by cutting height, but a 5-cm cutting height produced significantly